

SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON SOCIAL INTELLIGENCE

Avlaev Orif Umirovich

Chirchik state pedagogical university, associate professor of Psychology department,
Philosophy Doctor (PhD) on psychology

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7708380>

Abstract. *In this article, some comments on the role and importance of social intelligence in personality development are made. It includes the functions of social intelligence, its importance in personal activity, and recommendations for the development of social intelligence. Social intelligence is equated with cognitive competence, which enables people to foresee events in their lives and make effective use of them.*

Keywords: *social intelligence, cognitive competence, personal activity, verbal and non-verbal actions, analyzing your own feelings.*

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the consistent, systematic, organic, goal-oriented organization of education of young people, to make them work as active members of society, first of all, requires wide-scale and deep research of this issue as an actual pedagogical-psychological problem. The ability of young people to correctly assess the events of social reality, to have a personal opinion about social changes requires that they acquire certain social intellectual skills. In the last decade, the interest of researchers in psychology to the problems of understanding the mechanism of social management of behavior, the inclusion of a person in social relations and mutual actions, and the analysis of his real life in concrete socio - economic and historical conditions has become active. A more direct connection with the phenomena governing the behavior of the individual in the society is social intelligence. People with a high level of social intelligence are usually friendly, supportive, thoughtful, flexible in solving various social problems, and succeed effectively in society. They also have more confidence in social situations, show genuine concern for their companions, and express their feelings and emotions with clarity and determination. In addition, a high level of social intelligence can reduce interpersonal problems, mediation and conflicts, manage communication processes, and thus choose safe ways.

social intelligence, studied it as a system of intellectual abilities that is excluded from the factor of general intelligence and primarily related to the understanding of information related to behavior.

Tests created by D. Keating in the 80s were designed to evaluate moral or ethical thinking. M. Ford and M. Tisak argues that the basis of intelligence assessment lies in finding the correct solution to problematic situations. They were able to show that social intelligence includes a specific and proportional group of mental abilities related to information processing. This group of abilities is fundamentally different from the abilities that form the basis of "formal" thinking and are tested by "academic" intelligence tests[1-6].

N. Kentor equates social intelligence with cognitive competence, which enables people to know the events happening in their lives in advance and use them effectively.

The functions of social intelligence include:

1. Ensuring adequacy and flexibility in changing conditions;
2. formation of mutually successful programs and plans in tactical and strategic directions, solving current issues;

3. planning events in interpersonal relations and forecasting their development;
4. motivational function;
5. expansion of social competitiveness (IR);
6. self-formation, self-understanding, teaching oneself [10].

One of the main tasks of social intelligence is the formation of long-term mutual relations. Understanding the level and nature of mutual relations, it consists of positively influencing each other and strengthening relations in the future.

Social intelligence determines the neuro-psychic state for a certain time, the factors of the social environment and the success of social relations, provides the ability to save emotional stress, stress discomforts, emergency situations and personal crisis situations.

The mobilizing function of social intelligence, which helps in emergency crises, long-term stress, and understanding of self-respect, is very important.

Social intelligence provides an opportunity to predict and prepare for events that occur in relationships between people, and strengthens tolerance to psychological stress.

In contrast to the structure of general intelligence, in the structure of social intelligence, individual characteristics and characteristics of self-awareness play a large role. In this case, self-awareness should not be "difficult", filled with complexes and psychological barriers. That's why high indicators of social intelligence are very rare in a totalitarian person. Such a person experiences subtle difficulties when dealing with people, he has a bad understanding of people (for example, people of the opposite sex), he cannot get along with them, and sometimes he is completely afraid of people. Such a person is full of complexes due to the fact that his self-awareness is not developed. They have little or no personal interests, and are prone to aggression without realizing it.

In order to achieve success, a person must understand why he runs a business and what results he wants to achieve. These two factors determine motivation, that is, the main reasons why a person performs the necessary directed actions. Motives determined by time and the final result are called expedient. Any successful activity is always carried out in accordance with the purpose, and the extent to which the fully realized activity corresponds to the desires and ideals of the ultimate goal is another acceptable definition of success.

In the process of considering a personal activity or a specific goal, everything seems clear and does not cause special difficulties in understanding - if a person has achieved his goal, then this is success. But life does not end with one goal. And if the achievement of this goal excludes the possibility of achieving other goals? What should happen in their implementation? Does this situation fully meet our concept of success? Undoubtedly, before doing something about a certain goal, it is necessary to determine its other goals, as well as to establish a sequence and interdependence among them. Clarity and completeness with consistent life goals are the main guide to success in life and achieving them can be the meaning of life for everyone.

It is clear that it is almost impossible to clearly plan your life, to set specific goals with specific periods - the world and your own worldview are changing, attitudes and priorities, values and desires are changing. What does it look like to do something that makes you uncomfortable, something that can change? This is very true. However, the ability to live aimlessly, focusing on the satisfaction of short-term desires, on the principle that everything is now, strictly speaking, does not lead to long-term success. In this case, neither planning, nor forecasting, nor managing

one's activities in any long-term perspective is simply impossible. And the question of success remains completely unclear.

1. Goals determine success, and if there are goals, it will be clear what success can be, in what direction to move and what methods to use to achieve it. In this case, goals, especially for long-term goals, are not some static image-objects, but a vector direction in which life management is carried out, which includes predicting the possibilities of the situation and choosing the best option. actions, as well as the clarity of images as specific goals are defined and the application of actions to their implementation. In this case, everything is built in a clear, flexible and unpredictable way.

2. Our research has shown that the effective development of personal components of psychological health does not appear by itself under the influence of the situation and requires the creation of a special environment that encourages the child's self-development. Conditions of humanist creation

173 social and cultural development environment that provides the opportunity for meaningful communication of young adolescents with their peers and teachers in educational activities are: creation of an environment of openness, trust, non-violence and positive experience; lack of positive assessment of children's answers by teachers; creating a creative environment on parameters such as problem solving, information ambiguity and cooperation. Therefore, it is necessary to include a specially built psychological support service, which is implemented by a psychologist together with teachers, especially classroom teachers, in the educational process[6-12].

3. Work with adolescents, organized as a system of multidirectional interactions of children (young adolescents) with adults and peers at school, especially from the point of view of additional education, helped the development of the most important personal formation that constitutes the essence of social consciousness of subjects and age characteristics. Some parents try to limit their teen's social experiences to the school environment. This causes teenagers to be deprived of the opportunity to expand their communication circles and social practices.

4. It should not be forgotten that the socio-pedagogical competence of educators and educational psychologists is an important condition for achieving positive results in the development of the main components of social intelligence in young adolescents. It has been successfully developed in the process of integrated professional communication.

Conclusions and recommendations:

The authors include training, film therapy and video analysis, role-playing, problem-solving, empathic listening techniques, exercises for developing non-verbal communication tools, and role-plays on effective ways to increase the level of social intelligence. However, a person who wants to improve social intelligence must understand that this requires the development of other skills. For example, good attention. The importance of attention cannot be overstated, because sometimes there is an interest in some important details that help to better understand the interlocutor. When others can read automatically, a person with a low level of social intelligence needs to be brought to the level of consciousness: to pay attention to all the details in order to notice the important ones in the end.

1. people's *non-* verbal behavior (gestures, facial expressions, etc.): non-verbal signals sometimes provide more information for control than verbal signals. This skill will be very useful and it is very simple to develop it: you can turn on any unknown movie or series with the sound

off and try to make a conclusion about the emotions and the general situation on the screen based on the non-verbal behavior of the actors. In addition, it will not be difficult to test yourself by reviewing the same scenes with sound.

Analyze your "non-verbal" behavior. Be aware of yourself and your body and try to understand how the external signals of the body relate to your internal states and emotions.

2. *As for verbal communication*: talk about little and good information. Try to develop your skills by interacting with people who are willing to listen to you as much as possible. Identify your weaknesses and work on your mistakes. For example, if you notice that the person you are talking to does not understand your speech, practice until your speech is understandable to others.

3. *Analyze your feelings* . Try to understand what influenced the emergence of a certain emotional state that led to an acute reaction or allowed to soften it. Watch how this or that emotion affects your thought processes - then you will be armed. For example, if you find that you can't think at all when you're angry, then wait until your anger has subsided before you begin any task or conversation. Also, think about how to get rid of some harmful emotions in advance. If you realize that you are in a state of panic and confusion before each meeting with your bosses, you should think of individual methods aimed at reducing this situation.

REFERENCES

1. Avlaev OU, Abdujalilov Sh. A. The of social intelligence in personal maturity. International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation. Scopus. Voles. 24, Chair 06, 2020 ISSN: 1475-7 Page No. 428 – 436
2. Avlaev OU, Burkhanov , aa, handbook one dm, for Norkuzieva intellectual factor affecting the dynamic of the individual . “TEST engineering & management.” Scopus. May-June 2020 ISSN: 0193- 4120 page no. 693 – 702
3. Avlaev O. U. Gender differences of social intelligence in student development. Scientific journal "Psychology". 2021. № Pages 1, 34-41.
4. Bobneva M.I. Psychological problems of social development of personality. - M., 1979.
5. Gamezo M.V., Petrova E.A., Orlova L.M. Developmental and pedagogical psychology: Proc. manual for students of all specialties of pedagogical universities // Pedagogical Society of Russia. - 2004.
6. Ivanov A.A. Age aspects of social intelligence // Scientific research in education. - 2009, No.1.
7. Knyazeva N.N. The study of social intelligence in schoolchildren and students // Anniversary international scientific and practical . conf ., dedicated to the 200th anniversary of D.P. Oznobishin. - Samara, 2004.
8. Kunitsyna V.N. Social competence and social intelligence: structure, functions, relationship // Theoretical and applied issues of psychology / ed. A. A. Krylova. - St. Petersburg, 1995.
9. Luneva O.V. History of the study of social intelligence // ZPU. - 2008. No. 4.
10. Makarov A.V., Tsybulenkova T.S. Conditions for the development of social intelligence of preschoolers // Science time . —2015, No. 7 (19).
11. Nikolaevsky R.P. Development of social intelligence in student age // MNKO. - 2012, No. 5.
12. Panova N.V. Levels of development of the main components of the social intelligence of younger adolescents // Integration of education. - 2011, No. 2.